

Niementowski-4-Oxoquinazoline Synthesis : Part IV. Application to 3-Amino-2-Naphthoic Acid Derivatives.

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The condensations of 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid with various acid amides and of various 3-N-acylamino-2-naphthoic acids with formamide leading to the formation of 2-H, Me, CH₂Ph, Ph, *p*-NO₂Ph and *p*-OMePh-3H-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazolines have been studied systematically. Additional evidence in favour of the reaction mechanism proposed for Niementowski-4-oxoquinazoline synthesis has been provided.¹ UV spectra of these compounds have been studied in aqueous ethanol at different pHs. The spectra of these compounds in neutral medium are compared with those of their 3-Me and 3-Ph-substituted derivatives. 2-*p*-Nitrophenyl and 2-*p*-anisyl derivatives of 3-Me and 3-Ph-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazolines have been synthesised starting with the corresponding 2-arylbenzo(6,7)-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one.

Niementowski 4-oxoquinazoline synthesis has been extensively used for the synthesis of bz-substituted-2H and 2-methyl-4-oxoquinazoline derivatives^{2,3}. This reaction has been studied by Patel and Patel¹ with a view to isolating the possible intermediates involved in the reaction. These authors have proposed most probable mechanism for this reaction explaining the structure-reactivity relation¹. The present communication describes the results of the study of the application of the original and the modified Niementowski 4-oxoquinazoline synthesis to 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid and to 3-N-acylamino-2-naphthoic acid derivatives respectively. The results of this study has provided additional evidence in favour of the reaction mechanism proposed for this reaction. The UV spectra of 2R-3H-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazoline described in the present communication have been studied at different *p*Hs in aqueous ethanol. The spectral trends of these compounds have been compared with those of their corresponding 3-methyl and 3-phenyl derivatives. Syntheses of 2-*p*-nitrophenyl and 2-*p*-anisyl-3H-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazolines and their 3-methyl and 3-phenyl derivatives based on the reaction of 2-*p*-anisyl and 2-*p*-nitrophenyl-benzo(6,7)-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-ones with the required amine have been described.

The condensation of 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid with acid amides has been studied under varying experimental conditions (Table 1). For comparative study, the condensations of anthranilic acid with the above mentioned acid amides were carried out under identical conditions (Table 1). A comparative study of the yield of a 2R-3H-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazoline derivative formed on condensation of 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid (I) with a given acid amide with that of corresponding 2R-3H-4-oxoquinazoline formed on condensation of anthranilic acid with same amide under identical experimental conditions indicates that 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid (I) is more reactive than anthranilic acid in this reaction. This

difference becomes highly apparent when the results of the condensations of these acids with benzamide derivatives are compared. The acid (I) on condensation with *p*-nitrobenzamide, benzamide and *p*-anisamide afforded 2-*p*-nitrophenyl (II), 2-phenyl (III) and 2-*p*-anisyl (IV)-3H-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazolines in 68, 58 and 46% yields respectively.

TABLE 1

Reaction of 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid with R-CONH₂ : Synthesis of 2R-3H-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazoline

RCONH ₂	2R-3H-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazoline* R	Reaction Temperature °C	Yield %±2	m.p. °C	2R-3H-4-oxoquinazoline** yield %±2
HCONH ₂	H	140	80	278 ⁽⁵⁾	90
CH ₃ CONH ₂	Me	200	74	320 ⁽⁵⁾	42
Ph-CH ₂ -CONH ₂	CH ₂ Ph	200	70	270 ⁽⁴⁾	15
Ph-CONH ₂	Ph	200	58	294-96	In traces
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -Ph-CONH ₂	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ Ph	200	68	> 350	6
<i>p</i> -OMe-Ph-CONH ₂	<i>p</i> -OMePh	200	46	275-76	zero

* 3-Amino-2-naphthoic acid (1 mole) and R-CONH₂ (3 moles) heated at stated temperature for 3 hrs.

** Product formed in the condensation of anthranilic acid with the stated amide.

The order of reactivity of these benzamide derivatives is the same as that of the electrophilicity of the carbonyl-carbon atoms in *p*-nitrobenzamide, benzamide and *p*-anisamide molecules. The order of electrophilicity can be predicted on the basis of electronic effects. The condensation of anthranilic acid (V) with these benzamide derivatives afforded 2-*p*-nitrophenyl (VI), 2-phenyl (VII) and 2-*p*-anisyl (VIII)-3H-4-oxoquinazolines in 6, trace and zero per cent yields respectively. This indicated that the same order of reactivity of the amides is maintained in this series. In each of these reactions of V, the corresponding benzanilide derivative was also isolated from the reaction mixture. The formation of the latter type of compound would most probably be due to the decarboxylation of N-acylanthranilic acid which is supposed to have been formed as an intermediate in the first stage of the reaction.

The systematic study of the condensation of 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid (I) with *o*-chlorobenzamide furnished interesting results. In this reaction 3-*N*-*o*-chlorobenzamino-2-naphthoic acid (IX), 3-*N*-*o*-chlorobenzamino-2-naphthamide (X) and 2-*o*-chlorophenyl-3H-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazoline (XI) were isolated from the reaction mixture. This observation may be held as an additional evidence in favour of the reaction sequence proposed by Patel and Patel for the Niementowski-4-oxoquinazoline synthesis¹. According to the proposed reaction sequence this reaction is supposed to proceed through three stages viz; (i) formation of N-acylanthranilic acid, (ii) its transformation into N-acylanthranilamide and (iii) cyclodehydration of the latter to the corresponding 2R-3H-4-oxoquinazoline. The last stage of the reaction is an extremely facile one in absence of steric effect⁴. The yield

of the 4-oxoquinazoline derivative formed in the reaction of an anthranilic acid with a given amide would depend upon the ease with which the reaction would proceed in the first two stages of the reaction. This would ultimately depend upon the difference in the stabilities of the product-amide and reactant-amide molecules in each of the two stages of the reaction. It can be shown that the difference in the stabilities of the product- and reactant-amide molecules will be much more in the reaction of 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid (I) with a given

Chart-1

acid amide than that in the reaction of anthranilic acid with the same acid amide in each of the two stages of the reaction. This will explain why 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid is more reactive than anthranilic acid in this reaction.

The condensation of 3-N-acylamino-2-naphthoic acids with formamide was studied at different temperatures. The selected results are recorded in table 2. A comparison of these results with those of the original Niementowski-4-oxoquinazoline synthesis indicates

TABLE 2

Reaction of 3-N-acyl(R-CO)amino-2-naphthoic acid with formamide

3-N-acylamino-2-naphthoic acid	2R-3H-benzo(6,7) 4-oxoquinazoline R	Reaction Temperature °C	Yield % ± 2
3-N-Acetamino	CH ₃	150	85
3-N-Phenyl acetamino	CH ₂ Ph	150	75
		200	85
3-N-p-Nitrobenzamino	p-NO ₂ Ph	200	74
3-N-Benzamino	Ph	200	64
3-N-p-Anisamino	p-OMePh	200	55

that the modified method is superior to the original method in this series also. One more interesting observation providing evidence in favour of the reaction mechanism proposed for this reaction was furnished by the observation that the condensation of 3-*N*-*o*-chlorobenzamino-2-naphthoic acid (IX) with formamide afforded 3-*N*-*o*-chlorobenzamino-2-naphthamide (X) along with 2-*o*-chlorophenyl-3H-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazoline (XI).

The 3-substituted derivatives of 2-methyl, 2-benzyl and 2-phenyl-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazolines required for the comparative spectral study have been reported earlier⁵. 2-*p*-nitrophenyl and 2-*p*-anisyl derivatives of 3H(3-Me and 3-Ph)-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazolines were prepared by condensing 2-*p*-nitrophenyl (XIV) and 2-*p*-anisyl (XV)-benzo(6,7)-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-ones with required amines. The compounds XIV and XV were prepared by refluxing 3-*p*-nitrobenzamino (XII) and 3-*p*-anisamino (XIII)-2-naphthoic acids with acetic anhydride. Both these compounds were found to be highly stable. They could be kept in contact with water at room temperature without decomposition and could be crystallised from boiling ethanol. The reactions of both the compounds XIV and XV respectively with ammonia, aqueous methylamine and aniline were studied. The compounds XIV and XV did not react with ammonia even at 80°. The reaction could be effected by heating a mixture of XIV or XV and ammonium carbonate suspended in a mixture of liquor ammonia and ethanol at 100°. This led to the formation of 3-*N*-*p*-nitrobenzamino (XVI) or 3-*N*-*p*-anisamine (XVII)-2-naphthamides respectively. The compounds XVI and XVII on reaction with hot aqueous alkali afforded II and IV respectively.

The compound XIV reacted with 30% aqueous methylamine solution at room temperature and 50% ethanolic solution of aniline at 100° affording the corresponding 3-*p*-nitrobenzamino-2-*N*-methyl (XVIII) and *N*-phenyl (XIX) naphthamide respectively. XV was found to be less reactive than XIV. The compound XV reacted with methylamine solution at 80° yielding 3-*p*-anisamino-2-*N*-methyl naphthamide (XX) and with aniline only at reflux temperature affording corresponding anilide (XXI) derivative. The above mentioned 3-arylamino-2-*N*-methyl or phenyl substituted naphthamide derivatives were transformed into the corresponding 2-aryl-3-methyl (or 3-phenyl)-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazolines respectively by heating them at a temperature 5° above their respective melting points.

The UV spectra of all these 4-oxoquinazolines have been studied in aqueous ethanol containing 80% of ethanol at three different *p*Hs on Beckmann DU Spectrophotometer. The spectral data are reported in Table 3. An examination of these data reveals that the spectral trends of each of these compounds have not undergone any conspicuous change when the medium is made either strongly acidic or strongly basic. This is expected.⁶ Benzo (6,7)-3H-4-oxoquinazolines like simple 3H-4-oxoquinazoline would exist mostly in the keto form in solution and would be weakly basic.⁶ This presumption is further supported by the fact that the spectra of 2R-3H-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazolines and 3-substituted derivatives resemble each other very closely (Table 4).

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid (I) with o-chloro benzamide: A mixture of 2.0 g. of 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid and *o*-chlorobenzamide (3.5 g.) was heated at 200° for

TABLE 3

UV Spectral data of 2R-3H-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazolines in 80% aqueous ethanol in different media

R	Medium	β -band		para-band		∞ -band	
		max $m\mu$	log ϵ	max $m\mu$	log ϵ	max $m\mu$	log ϵ
H	neutral	238	4.55	310	3.63	340	3.46
		261	4.68	325	3.55		
		271	4.69				
H	acidic	241	4.54	310	3.68	340	3.54
		261	4.67	325	3.61	340	3.54
		270	4.71				
H	basic	239	4.84	305	3.61		
		260(s)	3.39	320	3.68		
		275(s)	4.32	325	3.71		
Me	neutral	237	4.52	296	3.64	360	4.53
		261	4.62	309	3.68	376	3.43
		271	4.70	323	3.57		
Me	acidic	244	4.44	310	3.58	353	3.52
		266	4.63	320(In)	3.52	370(s)	3.39
		275	4.60	335(In)	3.47		
		240	4.78	302	3.58	361	3.65
Me	basic	240	4.78	302	3.58	376	3.69
		261(s)	4.38	316	3.72	395(s)	3.44
		273(s)	4.29	330	3.72		
CH ₂ Ph	neutral	238(In)	4.48	296	3.48	345(s)	3.36
		262	4.70	311	3.59	365(s)	3.54
		273	4.72	325	3.52	385(s)	3.05
CH ₂ Ph	acidic	251	4.35	305(s)	3.38	355	3.53
		270	4.60	315	3.46	375(s)	3.30
		280	4.54	335	3.55		
CH ₂ Ph	basic	242	4.75	317	3.71	362	3.67
		255	4.53	330	3.71	375	3.78
		275	4.33			395(s)	3.49
Ph	neutral	239	4.57	340	3.97	---	---
		283	4.68	365(s)	3.77	---	---
				385(s)	3.36	---	---
Ph	acidic	238	4.50	341	4.82	---	---
		286	4.65	352(s)	3.80	---	---
				380(s)	3.51	---	---
Ph	basic	236	4.54	348	3.85	---	---
		265	4.64	366	3.84	---	---
		290(s)	4.48	381	3.84	---	---
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ Ph	neutral	240	4.54	340	4.16	---	---
		297	4.72	365(s)	3.90	---	---
				385(s)	3.47	---	---
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ Ph	acidic	243	4.56	313	4.64	---	---
				360(s)	4.06	---	---
				390(s)	3.69	---	---
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ Ph	basic	237	4.68	337(s)	3.87	---	---
		291	4.72	348	3.93	---	---
				367(s)	3.87	---	---
				385(s)	3.87	---	---
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ Ph	neutral	260	4.42	361	3.95	---	---
		299	4.18			---	---
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ Ph	acidic	253	4.42	361	3.89	---	---
		300	4.18			---	---
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ Ph	basic	251	4.54	385	3.97	---	---
		320-1(s)	4.18			---	---

TABLE 4

UV Spectral data of 2R-3R'-benzo(6,7)--4-oxoquinazolines in 80% aqueous ethanol

R	R'	β -band		para-band	
		max $m\mu$	log ϵ	max $m\mu$	log ϵ
H	H	237	4.54	311	3.64
		261	4.69	325	3.58
		271	4.70	340	3.42
H	CH ₃	238	4.58	316	3.71
		263	4.61	330	3.68
		273	4.62	340	3.64
Me	H	237	4.48	295(s)	3.57
		261	4.62	309	3.64
		271	4.65	323	3.54
Me	Me	239	4.65	301	3.65
		265	4.65	314	3.74
		275	4.67	329	3.71
Me	Ph	240	4.40	300	3.62
		264	4.54	315	3.65
		275	4.55	330(s)	3.41
Ph	H	239	4.51	341	3.91
		282	4.60		
Ph	Me	241	4.63	337	3.83
		277	4.68		
Ph	Ph	242	4.44	335	3.79
		277	4.55		
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ Ph	H	239	5.55	340	5.17
		296	5.69		
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ Ph	Me	239	5.60	332	4.95
		277	5.60		
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ Ph	Ph	240	5.57	340(s)	5.10
		277	5.62		
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ Ph	H	254	4.21	315(s)	3.83
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ Ph	Me	255	4.61	315(s)	4.02
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ Ph	Ph	265	4.62	315(s)	4.08

2 hrs. The cooled mass was treated with bicarbonate. The bicarbonate-insoluble solid was washed with hot 20% aqueous ethanol to remove *o*-chlorobenzamide and crystallised twice from boiling ethanol obtaining 0.2 g. 2-*o*-chlorophenyl-3H-benzo-(6,7)-4-oxoquinazoline (XI) as yellowish crystalline solid, m.p. 245° (Found : N, 9.4; C₁₈H₁₁ON₂Cl, requires : N, 9.6%).

The alcohol filtrate from above was diluted with water and the solid which separated was collected and crystallised thrice from 60% ethanol. 3-N-*o*-chlorobenzamino-2-naphthamide (X) was obtained as pale yellow needles, m.p. 236–38°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : N, 8.5; C₁₈H₁₃O₂N₂Cl, requires : N, 8.6%).

The bicarbonate-extract on acidification furnished 3-N-*o*-chlorobenzamino-2-naphthoic acid (IX). It was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 228°. (Found : N, 4.4, equiv. wt. 328; C₁₈H₁₂O₃NCl, requires : N, 4.3%, equiv. wt. 325).

This method is followed in the study of other similar condensations (Tables 1 and 2).

3-N-p-Anisamino-2-naphthoic acid (XIII) : It was crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish crystalline solid, m.p. 238°. (Found : N, 4.4, equiv. wt. 318. $C_{19}H_{15}O_3N$ requires : 4.3%, equiv. wt. 321).

2-p-Anisyl-benzo(6,7)-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (XV) : It was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 240–42°. (Found : N, 4.4; $C_{19}H_{13}O_3N$, requires : N, 4.6%).

3-N-p-Anisamino-2-naphthamide (XVII) : It was crystallised from 1 : 1 ethanol-acetic acid mixture in yellowish needles, m.p. 228–30°. (Found : N, 8.9; $C_{19}H_{16}O_3N_2$, requires : N, 8.7%).

2-p-Anisyl-3H-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazoline (IV) : It was crystallised from acetic acid in light-brown plates, m.p. 275–76°. (Found : N, 9.2; $C_{19}H_{14}O_2N_2$, requires : N, 9.3%).

3-N-p-Anisamino-2-N-methylnaphthamide (XX) : It was crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish needles, m.p. 206–08°. (Found : N, 8.1; $C_{20}H_{18}O_3N_2$, requires : N, 8.3%).

2-p-Anisyl-3-methyl-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazoline (XXII) : It was crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish leaflets, m.p. 165°. (Found : N, 8.7; $C_{20}H_{16}O_2N_2$, requires : N, 8.9%).

3-N-p-Anisamino-2-naphthanilide (XXI) : It was crystallised from acetic acid in brownish needles, m.p. 271–73°. (Found : N, 7.3; $C_{25}H_{20}O_3N_3$, requires : N, 7.1%).

2-p-Anisyl-3-phenyl-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazoline (XXIII) : It was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 210–12°. (Found : N, 7.3; $C_{25}H_{18}O_2N_2$, requires : N, 7.4%).

3-N-p-Nitrobenzamino-2-naphthoic acid (XII) : It was crystallised from acetic acid in silky needles, m.p. 274–75°. (Found : N, 8.4, equiv. wt. 332. $C_{18}H_{12}O_5N_2$, requires : N, 8.3%, equiv. wt. 336).

2-p-Nitrophenyl-benzo(6,7)-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (XIV) : It was crystallised from acetic anhydride in shining yellow needles, m.p. 268–69. (Found : N, 8.9; $C_{18}H_{10}O_4N_2$, requires : N, 8.8%).

3-N-p-Nitrobenzamino-2-naphthamide (XVI) : It was crystallised from acetic acid in tiny yellow needles, m.p. 264–65° (decomp.) (Found : N, 12.4; $C_{18}H_{13}O_4N_3$, requires : N, 12.5%).

2-p-Nitrophenyl-3H-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazoline (II) : It was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow crystalline solid, m.p. > 350°. (Found : N, 13.3. $C_{18}H_{11}O_3N_3$, requires : N, 13.2%). This compound afforded 2-p-nitrophenyl-3-methyl-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazoline (XXIV) described below, on treatment with methyl iodide in ethanolic alkali solution.

3-N-p-Nitrobenzamino-2-N-methylnaphthamide (XVIII) : It was crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish needles, m.p. 245–50°. (Found : N, 12.1; $C_{19}H_{16}O_4N_3$, requires : N, 12.0%).

2-p-Nitrophenyl-3-methyl-benzo(6,7)-oxoquinazoline (XXIV) : It was crystallised from 1 : 1 alcohol acetic acid mixture in pale yellow granules, m.p. 222–24°. (Found : N, 12.5; $C_{19}H_{13}O_3N_3$, requires : N, 12.7%).

3-*N*-p-Nitrobenzamino-2-naphthanilide (XIX) : It was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 264–65°. (Found : N, 10.1; C₂₄H₁₇O₄N₃, requires : N, 10.2%).

2-p-Nitrophenyl-3-phenyl-benzo(6,7)-4-oxoquinazoline (XXV) : It was purified by washing it with boiling acetic acid, yellow powder, m.p. 292–94°. (Found : N, 10.5; C₂₄H₁₅O₃N₃, requires : N, 10.7%).

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